

Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters

Deliverable D4.5

Demonstrations of the Knowledge Transfer Online Showcasing Module (KTOSM)

An AI-supported, interactive planning and monitoring tool to drive transfer, uptake, application and impact of Mission-Relevant Solutions.

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Authors: Caecilia Managò (ERINN), René Berndt (FhA), Alexander Dernild (SDU), Susana Bastón (CETMAR), Bossard, J. (CPMR), Cliona Nì Cheallachain (ERINN)

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

Table 1: Table of abbreviations and acronyms used in PREP4BLUE and the document

Acronym / Abbreviation	Signification
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CSA(s)	Coordination and Support Action project(s)
DoA	Description of the Action
EuroVoc	European Union's terminology database
(R)IA(s)	(Research and) Innovation Action project(s)
KER(s)	Key Exploitable Result(s)
KO(s)	Knowledge Output(s)
KT	Knowledge Transfer
KTOSM	Knowledge Transfer Online Showcasing Module
Mission	EU Mission 'Restore Our Oceans and Waters'
P4B	PREP4BLUE
RL	Readiness Level
T	Task
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The EU Mission 'Restore our Ocean and Waters' (hereafter 'the Mission') aims to restore by 2030 the health of one of our most precious common goods: our ocean and waters, as a major contributor to the European Green Deal, the Ocean Decade and the Sustainable Development Goals. PREP4BLUE's objective is to support the R&I goals of the Mission and facilitate its successful implementation, especially during this first phase (2022-2025), providing Methods and Tools. PREP4BLUE's Work Package 4 (WP4) will showcase pilot scale fit-for-purpose methods and tools to manage knowledge in support of the Mission.

One of the main outcomes of WP4 has been the development of the Knowledge Transfer Online Showcasing Module (KTOSM). This tool supports the EU Mission 'Restore our Ocean and Waters' by facilitating the transfer, uptake, and application of mission-relevant solutions. The KTOSM, an AI-supported interactive tool, aims to enhance knowledge management and impact monitoring by providing interactive stakeholder landscape mapping and facilitating development of Pathways to Impact for solutions with potential to support the Mission objectives.

This report describes the demonstrations of the KTOSM, an output of WP4 'Knowledge Management', reported under Task 4.4 'Knowledge Transfer of High Potential Mission Knowledge/ Solutions' led by Caecilia Managò (ERINN). It builds upon Tasks T4.1 'Develop the Mission Ontology as a Semantic network for all Mission Activities' led by René Bernd (FhA), T4.2 'Mapping and Visualisation of R&I Activity Relevant to the Mission' led by Alexander Dernild (SDU) and T4.3. 'Collect and Analyse Mission Knowledge/Solutions' led by Caecilia Managò (ERINN).

Thus, the KTSOM builds upon the preceding work under WP4 reported in the deliverables:

- [D4.1 Report on INITIAL VERSION of Mission ontology and semantic network and guidance for use](#)
- [D4.2 Report including the High potential KERs relevant for the Mission](#)
- [D4.3 Report on FINAL Mission ontology / semantic network and guidance for use](#)
- [D4.4 Report describing Mission Ecosystem DB and dedicated user interfaces for Mission end-users](#)
- [D4.5 Knowledge Transfer Online Showcasing Module](#) (Demonstration video)

The KTOSM aims to visualize linkages and identify synergies across solutions, projects, and stakeholders within the WaveLinks (WaveLinks.eu) platform. It enables interactive landscape mapping and the development of Pathways to Impact, as well as transfer impact monitoring. This tool is intended for knowledge owners, funding agencies, industry actors, policymakers, and civil society organizations. The KTOSM is based on a Knowledge Transfer Methodology developed by ERINN Innovation, which involves collecting knowledge, analysing potential target users, and developing Pathways to Impact. The tool's functional framework has the Mission ontology and a semantic network by FhA at its core, to structure and link data.

Several demonstrations of the KTOSM have been conducted, including live demonstrations, a demo video, and practical examples of Pathway to Impact development. These demonstrations have informed the development of key functionalities, such as stakeholder landscape mapping and graphical representation of Pathways to Impact. Practical examples illustrate the application of the Knowledge Transfer Methodology and the KTOSM, as well as its potential to support the Mission's objectives. The KTOSM empowers stakeholders to define impact indicators, fostering a democratised and co-creative approach to mission progress tracking towards the Mission Objectives and Targets.

Key Terms

Several specific terms are regularly used in this report. This section explains how these terms relate to each other. The definitions below may differ from other sources, but these are the adopted definitions for the purpose of PREP4BLUE's implementation.

Key Exploitable Result (KER): Knowledge Output identified as ready to transfer that has high potential to contribute to the Mission Objectives and Targets.

Knowledge Fellow: The person in PREP4BLUE partner organisation in charge of implementing the Knowledge Transfer methodology within the project.

Knowledge Transfer: The term for the overall process of moving knowledge between knowledge sources to the potential users of knowledge. Knowledge Transfer consists of a range of activities which aim to capture, organise, assess and transmit knowledge, skills and competence from those who generate them to those who will utilise them.

Knowledge Output: A unit of knowledge or learning generated by or through research activity. They are not limited to de-novo or pioneering discoveries but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior know-how/ knowledge.

Pathway to Impact: This can be one step, or a series of steps, required to carry a Key Exploitable Result to its Eventual Impact. Where there are a series of steps, it will include detailed mapping, the users involved at each step and their predicted role in the pathway to Eventual Impact.

Eventual Impact: The ultimate end benefit of the application of the Key Exploitable Result.

Transfer Impact: The demonstrable evidence that a Key Exploitable Result has travelled down a single step on the Pathway to Impact.

Target User: An individual(s) identified in a Pathway to Impact to whom a Knowledge Fellow will transfer the Key Exploitable Result.

End User(s): The individual(s) who will apply the Key Exploitable Result at the end of the Pathway to achieve the eventual Impact.

Ontology: is a branch of philosophy and computer science that deals with the study of existence, categorisation, and the relationships between different entities or concepts within a specific domain of knowledge. In the context of computer science and information systems, ontologies are used to represent and organise knowledge in a structured and formal manner.

Semantic Network: is a graphical representation of knowledge or information in the form of nodes (representing concepts or entities) and edges (representing relationships or links between concepts).

EuroVoc: EuroVoc is a multilingual, multidisciplinary thesaurus developed and maintained by the Publications Office of the European Union. It is a standardised vocabulary that serves as a tool for indexing, categorising, and retrieving documents and information related to the European Union (EU) and its institutions. EuroVoc is used primarily for the classification and retrieval of documents, making it easier to access and understand EU-related content in multiple languages.

Other Key Terms can be consulted in the [PREP4BLUE Glossary](#).

1 Background to the Knowledge Transfer Online Showcasing Module (KTOSM)

1.1 The KTOSM Knowledge Transfer Methodology

PREP4BLUE applies a tried and tested Knowledge Transfer Method, developed by ERINN Innovation. This method builds the framework for the Knowledge Transfer Online Showcasing Module.

© Image courtesy of ERINN Innovation

Figure 1: Knowledge Transfer Methodology by ERINN Innovation

The Methodology entails a deeply informed, three-step process, to collect knowledge, to analyse potential target user, and to develop Pathways to Impact. The main objective of the methodology is to plan, undertake and monitor transfer activities, and thus serves to foster and measure transfer impact.

The development of Pathways to Impact is deeply rooted in the Knowledge Management Methodology, which underpins [PREP4BLUE WP4 on Knowledge Management](#). In the Task 4.4 “Pathway(s) to Impact” are designed for high potential KERs identified in Task 4.3 as described in the deliverable [D4.2 Report including the High potential KERs relevant for the Mission](#).¹ In P4B T4.3, Key Exploitable Results were identified in interviews with knowledge owners, often the WP lead in EC funded projects. From this base, Key Exploitable Results (KER) were identified through the application of the PREP4BLUE Analysis Criteria. Currently, more than 100 KERs were described in Task 4.3, which are in the process of being signed off by the knowledge owners and subsequently being uploaded to the WaveLinks Solution Database: <https://wavelinks.eu/explore/solutions>.

¹ See Manago, C., & Ni Cheallachain, C. (2024). PREP4BLUE D4.2: Customized Knowledge Management Method for Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12527756>

1.1.1 PREP4BLUE Analysis Criteria

Analysis criteria (e.g., suitability, maturity, scale up, replicability, transformative, impact potential, systemic application) were developed, for assessing the suitability and potential of “knowledge/solutions” (e.g., methods, tools, data, information, technologies, processes) that can help achieve the Mission Objectives. The analysis criteria were deduced based on the Mission documentation available at the time of development, in 2022. The analysis criteria comprise a (non-exhaustive) summary of criteria and corresponding indicators (see Table 2), which were applied continuously across the steps of the Knowledge Transfer Methodology, informing:

- The identification and prioritisation of Knowledge Sources and KERs.
- The Stakeholder Landscape Mapping.
- The drafting of Pathways to Impacts towards the Mission Objectives and Targets.
- The prioritisation of the most efficient Pathway to Impact.
- The development of Transfer Impact Indicators and Outcome Indicators as basis for impact monitoring.

Table 2: Analysis Criteria and underlying Indicators

Criteria	Suitability*/ MISSION FIT (Contribution to target impacts...)	Application and Impact potential* By 2030	External factors and other considerations
Indicators	Mission Objectives, Targets, Enablers	Maturity* : Achievable Readiness-level (TRL, BRL, MRL, SRL, IRL)*	Market (CAGR, need, readiness) and market share (TAM, SAM, SOM)
	Policies, regulations or legislations the Mission is expected to contribute to (e.g. GreenDeal, SDG)	Scale-up* and scale out potential to maximise impact	User (identified, known, clear need identified, gains and pains across the value chain addressed)
	Protect and restore the health of our ocean and waters, climate neutrality, nature restoration	Replicability* (Geographical, Sectorial etc.)	Feasibility (e.g. a new standard to be implemented into a member state)
	In a specific Lighthouse area	Uptake potential (COM-B, TAM, TAC BCW)*	Competitors (strong competitor landscape or solution easy to copy)
	Innovativeness (transformative*, incremental, disruptive)*, beyond the State of the Art	Systemic application* (sub-system, system, ecosystem)	Resources needed for scaling (time, funds)
	Not highly innovative but high value to create impact.	Negative impacts (collaterals, risks, barriers, trade-offs)	Domain-specific considerations

1.1.2 Identification and Collection of Knowledge

At the collection step, solutions are identified and described through interviews and written up in standardised templates which are showcased on WaveLinks.

In Task 4.3, high potential knowledge is identified (based on the Analysis Criteria described in section 1.1.1), and Key Exploitable Results (KERs) are described by a dedicated group of ‘Knowledge Fellows’ led by ERINN (Leader of Task 4.3) in collaboration with CNR and CETMAR. This is followed by Analysis by means of expert panel discussions to inform the pathways of the KERs, organised and facilitated by ERINN. Transfer is then planned to take place where most appropriate, either by P4B itself or by Lighthouse CSAs/IAs, in Task 4.4. Through the task, and as defined in Deliverable D4.2, the following was achieved:

- **825 EU projects** were initially identified through AI technology as potentially having relevance to the Mission (see D4.4),
- the application of filter criteria (see D4.2) and Analysis Criteria (see chapter 1.2) refined this number to **96 projects with priority relevance** to the Mission.
- WP4 partners with responsibility for the identification of knowledge **contacted 113 projects** as they were also given the flexibility to contact projects, they were aware of as having high potential outputs.
- With an average response rate of 35%, **42 interviews were scheduled** and undertaken.
- This resulted in the identification of Key Exploitable Results (KERs). **103 KERs** have been described and identified as being **Key Exploitable Results (KERs)** with specific potential to impact upon the Mission.
- Currently, **40 KERs sourced by PREP4BLUE are uploaded** on WaveLinks' Solutions Database.

1.1.3 Analysis to Inform Pathways to Impact

The Analysis step informs the development of pathways to impact, based on expert panel discussions and desktop research. This can be supported through KTOSM Stakeholder identification and Landscape Mapping. This way, transfer activities can be informed, planned and undertaken, to foster application, uptake and ultimately impact. Pilots of informed Pathways to Impact are showcased in the KTOSM. The visualisation of Pathways to Impact allows for planning, as well as progress tracking towards the Mission Objectives, for each Solution uploaded to WaveLinks. Currently, examples of Pathways to Impact for certain KERs are provided for inspiration.

Six expert panels have been organised, analysing eight KERs per panel with 3 experts invited in each panel. More information on the Expert Panels can be found on the PREP4BLUE website: [Analysis for impactful Knowledge Transfer, successfully concluded in PREP4BLUE - PREP4BLUE](#).

1.1.4 Transfer and Measured Impact

In PREP4BLUE, and as reflected in the Analysis Criteria, eventual impact of each KER is identified based on its potential to contribute to the EU 'Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030', namely to its Objectives and Targets.

Target User and End-User are identified based on a landscape mapping, specific to the Key Exploitable Result, to identify the most efficient Pathway to Impact among the diverse potential Pathways to Impact.

Figure 2: From Key Exploitable Result to Mission Objectives and Targets

The Pathways to Impact serve the purpose to make the implicit explicit, showing the most efficient path towards the eventual impact. This long-term impact lays in the sphere of interest but cannot be directly influenced within the project lifetime. However, we map the full pathway to impact, to align every initial step to the sought long-term impact. This long-term impact is defined in the Mission context by the Mission Objectives and Targets.²

² See European Commission (2021): EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters Implementation Plan (https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/document/download/d6162cbd-6d09-48fd-b5b4-d7d2be69972c_en?filename=ocean_and_waters_implementation_plan_final.pdf)

1.1.5 Stakeholder Landscape Mapping to identify the most efficient Pathway to Impact

Just as when navigating in a Geomorphological landscape, a person trying to travel from A to B identifies the most efficient pathway. This selection is not only based on distance, but also on barriers (e.g., geomorphological elevations/ Mountains) and drivers (e.g., established roads or vehicles/ trains, ships, etc.), which shape the landscape and determine the pathways, their feasibility and velocity.

As the aim of the Mission is to reach the Mission Objectives and Targets by 2030, the most time-efficient pathway is sought, to bring a solution to its eventual impact. On that journey, diverse stakeholders need to adopt and apply the solution, as the application of knowledge drives impact. To identify the most efficient pathway among various options across potential target stakeholders, it is useful to map the Stakeholder Landscape - to make the implicit explicit - including the identification of barriers (e.g., lack of regulations) and drivers (e.g., established regulations, market growth and clear stakeholder needs). However, the first step is to identify stakeholders and potential target users.

Picture Courtesy: ERINN Innovation

Figure 3: Stakeholder Landscape Mapping from KER to Impact and most efficient Pathway to Impact identification.

Based on the landscape mapping, a bespoke Pathway to Impact is generated, including Target Users, corresponding transfer activities, application, the expected outcomes and impact indicators. In PREP4BLUE, the most efficient Pathway to Impact is identified in application of the Analysis Criteria. The most efficient Pathway to Impact represented as a green line on the right in Figure 3.

Picture Courtesy: ERINN Innovation

Figure 4: Description of the most efficient Pathways to Impact.

In PREP4BLUE, a custom knowledge transfer plan is then developed based on the first transfer step in the pathway per high priority KER to maximise change of uptake/application within the Mission LH Initiatives context. The transfer plan includes message, medium, channel and impact measurement. Two examples are described in the chapter 3.3. of this report.

2 Overview of the Knowledge Transfer Online Showcasing Module (KTOSM)

2.1 General description of the KTOSM

2.1.1 What is the tool?

The Knowledge Transfer Online Showcasing Module (KTOSM) is a visual, AI-supported, interactive tool embedded in WaveLinks (wavelinks.eu). The KTOSM is composed of currently three modules:

- A. A network graph, which enables exploring linkages across the solutions, stakeholders and Projects (in the future, also funding opportunities and policies relevant to the Mission can be linked).
- B. A ranking of Stakeholders, with its corresponding network graph, as well as filter-functions.
- C. Pathway to Impact visualisations: These are based on the PREP4BLUE Knowledge Management Methodology described in section 1 and enabled through the Mission Ontology and a Semantic Network, developed by FhA.

2.1.2 How the methodology informed the tool

The Knowledge Transfer Online Showcasing Module has two main purposes:

- **Showcase** how Knowledge Transfer can be undertaken systematically, ensuring both efficiency and effectiveness. For example, as outlined above, landscape mapping is a critical step to inform pathways to impact. The KTOSM makes this step more efficient.
- **Facilitate** the replication and application of the methodology, as well as the visualization of the Pathways to impact, to foster solutions' transfer, application, and impact towards the Mission Objectives and Targets.

Hence, the KTOSM showcases, how KT is systematically undertaken and provides visibility to each step of the methodology. The aim is to ease the replication of continuous application of the methodology to foster effectiveness and efficiency in KT in the Mission context.

	Identifies units of knowledge within a research project
	Describes knowledge in sufficient detail for analysis by experts
	Analysis process enables the development of a specific Pathway to Impact
	Enables the identification of user(s) and application(s)
	Develops customised transfer plans per user/application (s)
	Contains Measurement of Success indicators
	Is systematic, replicable & effective

Table 3: Features constituting the methodology

Table 3 above summarises the features that constitute the methodology, which were taken into consideration to build the KTOSM.

The KTOSM showcases the ‘Identification and Collection of Knowledge undertaken’ in PREP4BLUE, highlighting the description of solutions as illustrated by an example solution in the figure below (at the left of the KTOSM page). The ‘Mapped Pathways to Impact’ can be visualised, Stakeholder Landscape mapping facilitated, stakeholders are ranked (as shown in the modules at the right of the KTOSM page). Based on the Outcome Indicators identified for each solution, Transfer Impact can be measured.

Figure 5: How the methodology informed the tool

The KT Methodology forms the constituting and conceptual framework of the KTOSM. It was designed to showcase the efficient and effective application of the methodology, while also facilitating the steps through the Mission Ontology and Semantic Network (see 2.1.4 *The KTOSM Functional Framework*). In particular, it supports Stakeholder Mapping and Ranking to inform pathways to impact, complementing expert panels and desktop research.

2.1.3 Where can it be found?

To access the KTOSM the user needs to be registered on WaveLinks (wavelinks.eu/login). Registration can be done by clicking on Register (button on the up-right side of the screen). Once registered the KTOSM as well as all the Wavelinks resources can be accessed.

Figure 6. Screenshot of WaveLinks Log in site

Clicking on the “Solutions” tab in the left-hand menu, the Solutions Database can be accessed, with up to 139 Solutions uploaded between PREP4BLUE and [BlueMissionAA](#), as of March 2025 (see figure 7).

Figure 7: Screenshot of the Solutions tab in WaveLinks

WaveLinks offers category specific search functions. The Solutions can be filtered by Basin, Mission Objective, Readiness Level and Data Source (see Figure 7). A Key-word search provides the most individual search function.

Clicking on a PREP4BLUE sourced solution, the KTOSM per solution can be accessed, which shows the solution description on the left and the KTOSM Modules on the right (see Figure 8).

Cystoseira meadows mapping in the Mediterranean Sea: comprehensive georeferenced database.

Project website: [AFRIMED](#)

Background Description: Cystoseira sensu lato assemblages are being considered as habitats of critical importance for the EU (Directive 92/43/EEC Annex I, included in "Rocky reefs") and as indicators to assess ecological status in the context of the Water Framework Directive (WFD, Directive 2000/60/EC). There is a growing focus on the status of macroalgal forests from both a conservation (Annex II of the Barcelona Convention, COM(2009)0585(FIN)) and a restoration (with MERCEJ and AFRIMED projects) perspective to better understand the possibilities for reversing current declining tendencies through active restoration in the Mediterranean Sea. However, there is a lack of quantitative and standardised information on the distribution and temporal trends of the state of Mediterranean communities, due to the scarcity of available data (few studies have been conducted) and the use of different approaches for the various works conducted, which make it difficult to compare them.

Technical Description: The georeferenced database of Cystoseira was produced embedding catalogued grey literature, systematic review papers, EDONet (European Marine Observation and Data Network), previous database produced by FP7 EU project CoCoNet (Grant agreement no: 287844) and new data acquired from CARLIT (Cartography of Littoral and upper sublittoral benthic communities) monitoring program; however, data are missing for some areas (east and south). To overcome the lack of information, a Habitat Suitability Model (HSM) was developed by means of 55 predictor variables (geomorphologic, environmental and anthropogenic) using the Random Forest Machine Learning technique (789059 AFRIMED KDC). This database goes beyond the state of the art as it collects various datasets and improves them with a new predicting model (HSM, 789059 AFRIMED KDC) to identify suitable areas for 20 Cystoseira species ([here the list](#)) where data were not available as well as the above mentioned predictor variables that include, among others, factors related to anthropogenic pressures e.g. Artisanal fishing, Human impact to marine ecosystems and pollutants. The Habitat Suitability Model output, showing suitable areas for Cystoseira species across the Med, is described in the figure below.

Potential Impact And Applications: The database has potential commercial exploitation in that it may be uptaken by enterprises operating in marine restoration to determine which areas satisfy the requirements for restoration measures based on historical data and prediction model according to geomorphological features. Other than that, the main use that can be made is to provide policymakers with an overview of areas both for restoration activity but also to implement new protected areas since macroalgal forest provide several key ecosystem functions (nursery, feeding, etc.) and services (fishing, leisure, etc) that enhance biodiversity in the areas in which they are located. Other possible applications include gap assessments on carrying out restoration measures and assessments related to spatial planning. The map was created by considering geomorphological variables such as soil type, environmental variables such as temperature or pH, and anthropogenic variables such as distance from ports or the presence of tourists; it thus provides us with information on the different characteristics that describe the areas of the Mediterranean Sea. It is therefore possible to know where stress factors are present that can be removed or mitigated, to make the area suitable for restorative actions, suggesting to interested parties where to act and in so doing, reducing the economic expenditure for ineffective actions. These possible applications of the map contribute directly to the first Mission objective, to "Protect and restore marine ecosystem and biodiversity", in particular the restoration plan can "Contribute to

Readiness level: TRL 9 - Actual system proven in operational environment

Project: AFRIMED

Explore the Stakeholder Landscape

Potential Stakeholders Search stakeholders...
Country: Organization Type:
Loading...

Methodology behind the Online Showcasing module

Explore your Pathway to Impact

Draft your Pathway to Impact

Figure 8: Example of KTOSM per Solution

The KTOSM was designed to be a live tool, which makes it possible for project beneficiaries to upload descriptions of their KERs to the solutions page (see Figure 9).

WaveLinks Solutions

Fill the form to add a new solution to the database

Search [Add new](#)

Title *

General Description *

Keywords And Tags

Themes *

Mission Objective **Mission Targets**

Basin **Scale**

Readiness Level

Category *

Website

Mission Enablers **Mission Impact**

Financial Level **Provider ***

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PREP4BLUE BLUE-MISSION44 BLUE MISSION BANDS

Figure 9: Screenshot of the tab for adding a new Solutions to WaveLinks

2.1.4 The KTOSM Functional Framework

The KTOSM Functional Framework has the Mission Ontology and Semantic Network by FhA at its core.

The Mission Ontology, developed in PREP4BLUE, is used to represent and organize knowledge in a structured and formal manner.

The Mission Semantic Network is a graphical representation of knowledge or information in the form of nodes and edges.

Together, the Ontology and the Semantic Network allow to link and explore the data to get a better insight. The KTOSM uses both as a baseline to carry out the Stakeholder Mapping and Ranking.

Figure 10: Visual output of the Ontology and the Semantic Network

The Stakeholder Mapping allows to expand and contract the network by double-clicking on the different nodes listed in the legend, showing how the stakeholder, projects and solutions are interconnected.

Figure 10 shows the direct mapping of the solution to potential stakeholders, which share the same concepts (represented as EuroVoc terms/ Classification Nodes) extracted from the descriptions of the solution and the stakeholders.

EuroVoc is a multilingual, multidisciplinary thesaurus developed and maintained by the Publications Office of the European Union. It is a standardized vocabulary that serves as a tool for indexing, categorising, and retrieving documents and information related to the European Union (EU) and its institutions. EuroVoc is used primarily for the **classification** and retrieval of documents within the EU’s various language versions, making it easier to access and understand EU-related content in multiple languages. EuroVoc is used in ELI as a standardized and multilingual thesaurus that helps classify, index, and categorise legal documents within the EU.

This way, synergies can be identified and ranked. In this example (see Figure 11), one stakeholder shares all three EuroVoc terms/ Classification Nodes, one shares two EuroVoc terms/ Classification Nodes and the rest share only one EuroVoc term/ Classification Node with the solution (grey arrows in Figure 11).

Figure 11: Stakeholder Mapping

The list of Potential Stakeholders is ranked according to the linkages within the semantic network and shows the visual map as well (see Figure 12).

The similarity score ('Match score', see figure 12 below) shows how well stakeholders match the given solution, based on the number of shared EuroVoc terms between a stakeholder's projects and the solution, weighted by the number of projects matching the solution.

Potential Stakeholders Search stakeholders...

Country

Organisation Type

Stakeholder	Match score ?	Common terms	Actions
Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior De Investigaciones Cientificas	41.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> conservation of resources ecosystem biodiversity protection of animal life environmental 	View Graph

Found 88 potential stakeholders ?

Figure 12: Example of a list of Potential Stakeholders and Graph

2.2 Target user of the tool

The KTOSM is aimed at the following key stakeholders:

- **Knowledge Owner, such as Mission R&I Ocean Projects beneficiaries and NGOs, local communities and SMEs, as well as knowledge brokers and knowledge transfer and impact officers**, who aim to transfer their knowledge.
- **Mission Funding agencies and service provider** who aim to monitor the impact of transfer towards the Mission Objectives and Targets.
- **Industry actors, practitioners, policy makers and civil society organizations**, looking for uptake of solutions to address their needs for innovation.

This tool will allow stakeholders to gain better understanding of how their work fits into the Mission Ocean and Waters ecosystem, enhance awareness of other stakeholders working in their area of interest, provide users with an introduction to the legal considerations and regulatory environment they are working in making them aware of other research that could support their activities. The KTOSM provides a tool to support target user identification through the Stakeholder Mapping. This way, solutions can be identified and Pathways to Impact can be informed, drafted (including Transfer Activity, Target User, Application, Outcome and Impact Indicators), transfer activities undertaken and impact measured and monitored, both ex-ante and ex-post. The ex-ante Pathway to Impact development supports the planning and foresight on potential impact. The ex-post Pathway to Impact development can support the visualization of Narratives of Impact, allows dissemination of transfer success, storytelling and overall ex-post impact monitoring.

2.3 Advantages of using the tool

The KTOSM allows stakeholders to:

- Find, filter and identify solutions to a specific topic/issue/need;
- Enhance visibility and findability of their Key Exploitable Result;
- Map stakeholders working in their area of interest;
- Draft Pathways to Impact in a graphical representation;
- Identify Synergies across Solutions, Projects and Stakeholders;
- Track impact based on the outcomes and impact indicators at pilot scale;

Functions available at pilot scale but can be enhanced in further improvements of the KTOSM:

- When Funding and Policy & Legislation databases are available on WaveLinks, these can be linked as well to the solutions, to inform the pathways to impact.
- Accumulated impact monitoring, both ex-ante and ex-post transfer activities, to track and predict Mission Progress and feature Transfer Success (uptake and application) and related impact.

By enhancing understanding of the landscape in which a project's KER resides, and building upon examples of successful stakeholder engagement and interaction of past projects, the KTSOM aims to provide an easy and user-friendly mechanism for data and information collection. This supports the development of a robust Pathway to Impact for a specific KER. In PREP4BLUE, pathways to impact are integral to the knowledge transfer methodology, ensuring the most efficient and effective transfer activities are carried

out to achieve measurable impact in the Mission. Additionally, they enable the monitoring of transfer impact towards the Mission’s Objectives and Targets.

With the Knowledge Transfer Online Showcasing Module (KTOSM) we provide a pioneering, AI-supported, interactive planning and monitoring tool to drive transfer, uptake, application and impact of Mission-Relevant Solutions, based on a fit for purpose Methodology. The bottom-up approach in the development of Pathways to Impact in the KTOSM empowers the stakeholders who generate the impact to define the impact indicators. This underpins the democratisation of the Mission and its progress monitoring, while also fostering its co-creative nature.

2.4 How to use the tool and why

Based on the Demonstrations of the KTOSM (see chapter 3), we have consistently identified three main needs for AI support across the application of the Knowledge Transfer Methodology:

- NETWORK ANALYSIS: *e.g.* stakeholder landscape mapping
- MONITORING: *e.g.* impact tracking per solution
- SYNERGIES: *e.g.* between stakeholders, projects and solutions

Therefore, the main features of the KTOSM address exactly these user needs.

Complementary, but not replacing Expert Panels and Desktop Research, Stakeholder Landscape-mapping and target user identification is informed through the KTOSM, transfer impact monitoring enabled, and synergies can be identified.

The following figure (see Figure 15) shows the Stakeholder Landscape Mapping provided by the AI-supported KTOSM.

Figure 15: Example Stakeholder Landscape Mapping on WaveLinks

This feature, Stakeholder Landscape Mapping, has a vast potential to connect the right dots to foster impact, leveraging solutions and stakeholders towards contributing more to the Mission Objectives and Targets, by connecting them, to achieve jointly more than in silo.

Figure 16: Showcasing of Pathway to Impact per Solution

The Pathways to Impact are customised to the specific Key Exploitable Result, with a focus on the ‘Eventual Impact’ to be achieved. Both, the Pathways to Impact and each of its assets, such as the outcome indicators are developed in a bottom-up approach. The aimed ‘Eventual Impact’ contributes to the Mission Objectives and Targets. The Pathway from the ‘Key Exploitable Result t’ to the ‘Eventual Impact’ follows a two-way dynamic that underpins the Pathway to Impact approach. The Pathway goes from the ‘Key Exploitable Result’ to the ‘Eventual Impact’ through the steps which are ‘Transfer Activity’, ‘Target Users’, ‘Applications’, ‘Outcomes’ and corresponding ‘Impact Indicators’ per step. It also flows from the ‘Eventual Impact’ (contributions to the Mission Objectives and Targets) back to the necessary transfer activities required to achieve them.

As each person responsible to bring the Knowledge along the pathway to generate impact (this may be the Knowledge Owner, a Knowledge-Broker, etc.) defines the expected outcomes of the transfer activities and the corresponding Output Indicators. This way, these outcome indicators are developed bottom-up by the Mission Stakeholders.

Moreover, Knowledge Owners can track their outcomes as well as the impact of the transfer activities implemented. The added transfer impacts of several outputs combined can provide insights in accumulated impact per cluster or project with several outputs. The accumulated outcomes and their indicators can provide a realistic insight to track progress towards the Mission Objectives and Targets.

The bottom-up approach empowers the stakeholder who generates the impact to define the impact indicators, underpinning a democratisation of the Mission, as well as fostering its co-creative nature.

These are the guiding principles for PREP4BLUE, as well as the development of the KTOSM.

3 Demonstrations of the Knowledge Transfer Online Showcasing Module (KTOSM)

Five main demonstrations of the KTOSM were undertaken, each with a specific purpose:

1. **The initial live demonstration of the KTOSM** served to gain external stakeholder feedback to focus the further developments on the most needed functionalities (ca. 50 attendees).
2. **The second live demonstration of the KTOSM** served to showcase the latest functionalities at highest level of stakeholders at the Ocean Days 2025 (ca. 120 attendees).
3. **The demonstration of Pathway to Impact development, informed by the KTOSM as practical examples**, showcases how the KTOSM is piloted in PREP4BLUE in two practical use cases (21 pilots developed in PREP4BLUE, two showcased in chapter 3.3 of this report).
4. **The virtual demonstration at the BlueMissionAA Weekly Hour** had the purpose to make the KTOSM more known to target stakeholders, so the tool may be used broadly (26 online participants and 13 visualisations on YouTube within the first 24 hours post release).
5. **The main demonstration of the KTOSM: a demo-video** that explains how to access the tool, the methodology and ontology it is based on, as well as to demonstrate its functionalities as use-guide (27 unique viewers in the first 30 days after its launch).

These demonstrations, as well as the features that were developed along the process and different activities, are described below.

3.1 Initial live Demonstration of the KTOSM

The first live demonstration of the KTOSM was held at the BlueMissionBANOS Arena III, in Amsterdam on November 26, 2024, showing its first feature of a pondered list of stakeholders, matched by means of the Ontology, and a graph to view the matching by the Ontology.

The KTOSM was first presented in plenary, and then working groups were set up with a live demonstration and interaction of the stakeholders *in-situ*.

Figure 17: First functionalities of the KTOSM

This key first feature (see Figure 17) of the KTOSM is that it matches Solutions with Stakeholders. Figure 17 shows how the Stakeholder Matching is identified using the shared terms between the description of the solution and the description of research projects in which the stakeholder took part and ranked by the number of shared terms. Furthermore, the list of stakeholders can be filtered based on the Country and Organization Type. A Key-Word search allows a most individualised filtering and ranking.

The aim of this workshop was to collect user’s feedback on that functionality, as well as the needs for potential future functions. Feedback was very positive, with stakeholders finding the module very useful, with great potential for further application.

Main feedback was provided to prioritise the following functionalities, based on the user needs:

- NETWORK ANALYSIS: e.g. stakeholder landscape mapping.
- MONITORING: e.g. impact tracking per solution.
- SYNERGIES: e.g. between stakeholders, projects and solutions.

3.2 Second Live Demonstration of the KTOSM

During the Ocean Days 2025, on March 3, 2025, the Knowledge Transfer Online Showcasing Module was presented by ERINN Innovation (WP4-Lead) in the Joint Workshop on *“Harmonizing KPIs and approaches to support development of joint Mission Ocean and Waters monitoring framework”*.

The presentation showed how the Knowledge Transfer Methodology, and how the Identification & Collection of Knowledge, the Mapped Pathways to Impact and the Measured Impact of Transfer, are put into practice in the KTOSM. Three new/ improved modules (the Stakeholder Landscape Mapping, the stakeholder ranking and filtering, the Pathway to Impact visualisation) addressing the user needs identified in the first workshop, were presented:

With these new Modules, the KTOSM makes monitoring and output indicators practical for implementation, as they are tailored to each transfer activity and specific to a Key Exploitable Result.

Figure 18: Demonstration of the Methodological Approach of the KTOSM and how it is put into practice

The workshop provided the five Coordination and Support Actions (CSAs), which support the first phase of the [EU ‘Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters’](#), with the opportunity to take a first step towards ‘harmonizing KPIs and approaches to support the development of joint Mission Ocean and Waters monitoring Framework’.

Representatives from Mission Projects engaged in two panel discussions, debating challenges in KPI identification, implementation, and scalability, as well as ensuring KPI adoption and integration into Mission Projects.

The presented approaches and the exchanges in the panel discussion aimed to provide the foundation to drive the second phase (the ‘implementation phase’) of the EU Mission, ensuring that existing efforts can be leveraged rather than reinvented.

To the question ‘what dimensions might be overlooked in the monitoring frameworks and should be integrated’, it was pointed out that ‘*considering the local dimension and building on local communities’ knowledge is crucial*’.

In that sense, in this first step towards harmonising approaches, to capture diverse stakeholder perspectives from the start, the representatives' presentations on methods to drive and monitor impact towards the Mission objectives were combined with interactive sessions supported by live polls.

Figure 19: Interactive poll to identify user needs

To the question ‘What is the biggest challenge in KPI alignment across projects’ (see Figure 19), the main challenge identified, was ‘Making Indicators practical for implementation’.

The KTOSM can be a very practical tool, aligning the impact indicators to each transfer activity per Key Exploitable Result of, for example, a project. The added outcomes and corresponding impact indicators can, in the future, provide a realistic overview on how the diverse contributions at solution-scale contribute to the overarching three Mission Objectives and Targets.

3.3 Demonstration of Pathway to Impact Development, informed by the KTOSM, as practical examples

In PREP4BLUE, Pathways to Impact were developed for 21 KERs, identified in expert panels as of high priority to the Mission. In this section, we present two examples of Pathways to Impact, developed based on the expert panels held in PREP4BLUE, and additionally complemented through the KTOSM Stakeholder

Mapping. These expert panel discussions were facilitated in the ‘Analysis-step’ of the methodology. The development of pathways in P4B T4.4 helped to identify needs in the process of Pathway to Impact development, that the AI supported KTOSM could address. One key need was to support the Stakeholder Landscape Mapping and stakeholder ranking to identify potential target users. Therefore, these functions were addressed with the KTOSM. Since the Stakeholder Landscape Mapping was primarily informed through expert panel discussions and desktop research, when the KTOSM was in development, we present here a comparison of the results from both approaches.

3.3.1 Example Pathway to Impact for ‘iAtlantic Geonode’

This Pathway to Impact, developed by CETMAR, applied the described methodology for the KER “iAtlantic Geonode”. The full description of the KER can be found on [Wavelinks: https://wavelinks.eu/explore/solutions/339](https://wavelinks.eu/explore/solutions/339).

An extensive field programme comprising more than 30 research expeditions that collectively span the length and breadth of the Atlantic Ocean took place within the iAtlantic project. Drawing on a multinational fleet of research vessels and the latest marine technology and instrumentation. Its effort focuses mainly (but not exclusively) on 12 locations in the deep sea and open ocean that are of international conservation significance and of interest to Blue Economy and Blue Growth sectors. The iAtlantic [Geonode](#) is an open-source platform that facilitates the creation, sharing and management of geospatial information, ensuring the long-term visibility and impact of iAtlantic data beyond the duration of the project.

Researchers and institutions should ensure their data is publicly available, following appropriate protocols for data security. To the iAtlantic Geonode, seven groups put information together: [EMODnet](#), [GEOMAR](#), [Seascope](#), [Ifremer](#), [iAtlantic Consortium](#), [Marine Geospatial Ecology Lab at Duke University](#) and [Pangaea World Data Centre](#).

The first step in developing the Pathway to Impact is to identify the expected outcome, the eventual impact, and how it will contribute to the Mission Ocean and Waters objectives, as shown in the figure below (Figure 20).

From KER to Eventual Impact

Figure 20: Overview of the pathway to impact for ‘iAtlantic Geonode’

The second step is to create the Landscape mapping. In this case, the pathways were developed based on expert panel discussions and desktop research, including the consultation of the KTOSM. The main groups of stakeholders (see Figure 21) identified at the landscape mapping were:

- a) other EU funded projects,
- b) RTOs,
- c) Clusters and courses providers,
- d) Regulation & Standardisation agencies,
- e) Marine & offshore policymakers,
- f) Industry and
- g) Earth and Environmental sites.

Project owners had already developed a strong collaboration effort and reached impact. They had built partnerships with other regional marine observation and data initiatives through the Atlantic Ocean, e.g. EMODnet.

Landscape Mapping

The Landscape mapping is developed based on a discussion of an expert panel and desktop research. It serves the purpose to identify potential target users, to show the interrelation between stakeholders and to identify drivers and barriers along potential pathways to impact.

Map's logic: Through iAtlantic Project, EMODnet is building stronger partnerships with other regional marine observation and data initiatives and services, including the South African Environmental Observation Network (SAEON)

SOURCES OF INFORMATION

- 0.1 KO-owner as source of information
- 0.2 Expert Assessment in Analysis Meeting a source of information
- 0.3 WaveLinks as source of information (<https://wavelinks.eu/explore/solutions/339>)

LEGEND

Figure 21: Example of the Stakeholder landscape Mapping for 'iAtlantic Geonode'

Once the most comprehensive landscape was created, the third step is to identify the most efficient pathway to impact among all the possible pathways. In this case, the most direct application of the Geonode would be its use in research, but clear applications for the offshore industry were also identified. Its use by policymakers, as well as the regulatory and standardisation agency, was envisaged through EU funded project partnerships. Strengthening collaboration with other Earth and Environmental sites and

increasing the number of Geonode’s users through specific courses, as shown in Figure 22, seem to be the most efficient pathway to impact.

Pathway to impact summary

Step 1

Step 2

Figure 22: Example of Pathway to impact for ‘iAtlantic Geonode’

The iAtlantic Geonode can significantly advance scientific research, conservation efforts, and public awareness. Collaboration with institutions like the Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS), which provides open-access data on marine biodiversity, was considered to enhance data integration and dissemination. At the same time, the opportunity to develop tutorials, workshops, and documentation to educate users on effectively utilising the platform was also explored.

The figure below (Figure 23) illustrates how the transfer should be conducted and proposes a method for measuring the knowledge transfer’ impact.

Transfer Plan

Step 1	
Target User	Dan Lear (OBIS UK)
Transfer activity	
Channel	Email
Medium	Direct communication
Message	We would like to share with you the datasets available at the iAtlantic Geonode for the Atlantic deep-sea and explore potential collaborations
Application	Explore data exchange and further collaboration
Outcome	It is expected to be useful in research to better understand the species distribution on abyssal ecosystems. Besides, this collaboration might help to marine planners and decision-makers to identify, better manage and protect the biodiversity-rich areas of
Transfer impact	
Impact indicator	Interest from OBIS to include information from the iAtlantic Geonode to their dashboard
Impact measurement	Number of meetings undertaken for the agreed joint development

Figure 23: Example of the transfer plan for the specific KER for 'iAtlantic Geonode'

In the Stakeholder Landscape-Mapping for the iAtlantic Geonode by the KTOSM, two companies were identified (see pink octagon in Figure 24) in relation with this solution: Ocean Science International and Aquatec Group Ltd. Within the blue circle is the title of a project, NAUTILOS, which may be of interest to explore collaboration with.

Figure 24: AI-Supported Stakeholder landscape Mapping for 'iAtlantic Geonode'

The AI supported Stakeholder Mapping by the KTOSM (see Figure 24 above), shows complementarity to the main potential target user identification, which is informed through expert panels and desktop research. It includes:

- a) other EU funded projects,
- b) RTOs,
- c) Clusters and courses providers,
- d) Regulatory & Standardization agencies,
- e) Marine & offshore policymakers,
- f) Industry and
- g) Earth and Environmental sites.

This demonstrates that the KTOSM can help identify target stakeholder, especially in prioritising/ranking the stakeholders, and linking to specific organisations and their corresponding webpage.

The figure below (Figure 25) shows the structure of the pathway within the KTOSM, which has the fields a) Transfer activity, b) Target user, c) Application, d) Outcome, e) Impact indicator, following the KT methodology.

The KTOSM drafts the key steps for helping Mission Ocean and Waters stakeholders to develop transfer to Pathway to Impacts. As you can see, the two steps are filled, one enhancing collaboration with OBIS ([Ocean Biodiversity Information System](https://obis.org/), see <https://obis.org/>) and the other with the OceanTeacher website ([Home | OceanTeacher Global Academy](https://classroom.oceanteacher.org/), see <https://classroom.oceanteacher.org/>)

Figure 25: KER-specific Pathway to Impact Summary on WaveLinks for 'iAtlantic Geonode'

3.3.2 Example Pathway to Impact for 'Toolbox of solutions and measures for the good management of marine litter in aquaculture'

Another example for a Pathway to Impact was developed by CPMR, applying the described methodology in the case of the KER 'Toolbox of solutions and measures for the good management of marine litter in aquaculture' – in the following 'Toolbox'. The description of the KER can be found on [Wavelinks](https://wavelinks.eu/explore/solutions/306): <https://wavelinks.eu/explore/solutions/306>.

The Toolbox is one of the main outcomes of the AQUA-LIT project. The Toolbox showcases measures to prevent, monitor, remove and recycle marine litter from the aquaculture and fisheries sectors, and provides a strong support to the industry to develop in a more sustainable way. It also maps port reception facilities for marine litter in Europe, as well as funding, grant and investor opportunities available to aquaculture stakeholders at EU, national and trans-regional level. The Toolbox is also very collaborative, offering an open space for stakeholders to provide data and feedback on solutions for improved marine litter management. Citizens can get access to the Toolbox, which is also available in the form of a mobile app.

The following suggested Pathway to Impact is a first proposal to ensure the transfer of the Toolbox to target users, based on the expert panel discussions. It notably focuses on the dissemination of the Toolbox in other sea-basins, concretely the Atlantic and the Black Sea basin, and identify potential transfer activities.

Figure 26 shows the framework of the Pathway to Impact, by highlighting the expected outcomes of the Toolbox and eventual impacts. As reflected in the expert assessment, by providing solutions to reduce marine litter in aquaculture, the Toolbox is particularly aligned with Mission objective 1 and 2, as well as the third objective for a circular and low-carbon blue economy. Facilitating the contribution of citizens to the Toolbox, notably via the app, it also aligns with the Mission enabler to enhance public mobilisation.

From KER to Eventual Impact

Figure 26: Overview of the pathway to impact for the “Toolbox”

The next lines showcase how this pathway was developed and detail each step to reach the eventual impact, contributing to the Mission objectives and targets.

As described in the methodology, a Stakeholder Landscape Mapping was undertaken, to see the different potential pathways to impact (see Figure 27).

The Toolbox is applicable to the Mediterranean, North Sea, and Baltic areas and its strong potential for application in other geographical areas was particularly highlighted in the expert assessment. The Landscape Mapping therefore focused on the identification of Target Users in the Atlantic and Black Sea basins. In both cases, aquaculture farmers were identified as End-User, and the secretariats of regional sea conventions and sea-basin initiatives were considered as relevant intermediate Target Users. For

example, in the Atlantic: the OSPAR Convention Secretariat and the Atlantic Mechanism for the Atlantic Action Plan; in the Black Sea: the Secretariat of the Convention for the protection of the Black Sea Against Pollution, the Black Sea Assistance Mechanism for the Common Maritime Agenda for the Black Sea.

Landscape Mapping

Figure 27: Example of the Stakeholder Landscape Mapping for the 'Toolbox'

Figure 28: Example of the AI-Supported Stakeholder landscape Mapping for the 'Toolbox'

As illustrated in the above in Figure 28, complementary to the Stakeholder Landscape mapping undertaken based on Expert Panel information and Desktop Research, the KTOSM identifies the COHAB Initiative (<https://cohabinitiative.org>) and its corresponding Secretariat as key potential target stakeholders. This demonstrates that the KTOSM can add value to desktop research for target-user identification.

In application of the Analysis Criteria, and informed through the Expert Panels and Desktop Research, the most efficient Pathway to impact was identified (Figure 29).

The most efficient pathway

The most efficient pathway identified is the one using the support from sea-basin initiatives (Atlantic and Black Sea) to ensure the transferability of the toolbox in other sea basins.

In particular, the Black Sea Common Maritime Agenda Stakeholder Conference, and the Atlantic Stakeholder Platform Conference, gather once a year all the main stakeholders, project managers of these two specific sea basins. They can serve as catalyst to reach out to aquaculture farmers and policy makers of these sea basins to foster the adoption/uptake of the good practices and knowledge of the toolbox.

This can take the form of a presentation of AQUA-LIT toolbox during a session dedicated to marine conservation or environmental practices in the aquaculture/fisheries sector.

Prior lobby activities might need to be conducted (EC representatives, relevant pillar coordinators) so to ensure that this topic is at the agenda of the conference.

Basic networking can be done in parallel, as well as communication via the sea basin initiatives channels.

Figure 29: Example of Identification of the Most Efficient Pathway for the 'Toolbox'

Moreover, a Supporting Pathway (see Figure 30) was identified. It consists of organising multi-stakeholder roundtables to boost collaboration among all relevant actors, such as aquaculture farmers, port authorities, NGOs or equipment producers. This can notably enhance data collection to nurture the content of the Toolbox, as specifically identified in the expert assessment.

Pathway to Impact for the 'Toolbox'

Figure 32: Example of Pathway to impact for the 'Toolbox'

As illustrated in Figure 32 above, for both target sea-basins, the Atlantic and the Black-Sea, the target user 'Aquaculture Farmers' and conventions and corresponding secretariats are identified as target user.

The transfer-plan as shown below (see Figure 33) provides a step-by step guidance for activities to be undertaken towards the expected outcomes.

Transfer Plan

	Step 1	Step 2
Target User	Aquaculture farmers	Sea-basin initiatives (e.g. LH-CSAs)
Transfer activity	Roundtables with relevant stakeholders (e.g; port authorities, certification bodies, equipment producers, NGOs, scientists)	Participation annual conference
Channel	Invitations (via emails, social media, WhatsApp, other relevant channels)	Email to Secretariat, such as Assistance Mechanisms
Medium	Roundtable meetings	Speaker in a relevant thematic session
Message	Presentation of the toolbox with existing solutions to be potentially implemented in the Sea Basins	Presentation of the toolbox and invitation for potential collaboration in the sea Basins to facilitate the dissemination and uptake of the toolbox
Application	Raise awareness	Raise awareness and generate interest to collaborate to co-design implementation measures
Outcome	Awareness raised	Toolbox showcased
Transfer impact	Target user is aware of the toolbox	Potential co-design of implementation measures
Impact indicator	Statements of interest and potential agreements between stakeholders on measures to reduce marine litter	Statements of interest to collaborate
Impact measurement	At least one solution will be transferred in the Sea Basins	At least one statement of interest to collaborate for designing implementation measures in the Sea Basins

Figure 33: Example of the transfer plan for the 'Toolbox'

The figure below (Figure 34) shows how this information can be showcased in the KTOSM on WaveLinks.

Figure 34: KER-specific Pathway to Impact Summary on WaveLinks for the 'Toolbox'

3.4 Virtual Demonstration at the BlueMissionAA Weekly Hour

On March 26, 2025, from 2 to 3 PM CET, SDU, S.Pro and ERINN were invited by Prep4Blue’s sister project, BlueMissionAA to present the KTOSM as a feature of WaveLinks, in an interactive webinar exploring WaveLinks, a dynamic open-access platform designed to connect ocean stakeholders, foster collaboration, and drive innovative solutions in the marine and maritime sectors.

During the webinar it was illustrated how WaveLinks platform key functionalities and how it can support stakeholders’ work. Stakeholders could learn about ongoing projects and key stakeholders, explore the citizen science database and the engagement methods factsheet, and discover how cutting-edge protection and restoration solutions are shaping the future of our oceans. Additionally, a step-by-step guide was provided on how stakeholders can contribute to the platform.

This was a unique opportunity to connect with experts, gain valuable insights into collaborative initiatives, and leverage WaveLinks to amplify the impact on ocean conservation.

Figure 35: Watch the recording of the Demonstration at the BlueMissionAA Weekly Hour

The recording of the webinar can be accessed in the following link: [Atlantic & Arctic Lighthouse Weekly Hour on Unlocking Wavelinks \(S3E11\)](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xcRsAk7WBM&t=2s) (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xcRsAk7WBM&t=2s>).

3.5 Main Demonstration of the KTOSM: a demo-video

A recording of the KTOSM was developed by the relevant task leaders to explain the tool, the underlying framework and database as well as the intended use by stakeholders. This recording is the official demonstration of the KTOSM and is available on WaveLinks, as well as through the PREP4BLUE website and has been disseminated through all project communication channels through the following link: <https://wavelinks.eu/video/KTOSM-demo>.

Figure 36: Watch the KTOSM Demonstration Video

In the video, the click-path to access the KTOSM on WaveLinks is shown, as well as where and how a new solution can be submitted. Furthermore, the methodological background is explained, demonstrating how the three steps of the method are mirrored in the practical models of the KTOSM. It also showcases how the Ontology can be applied to support knowledge management.

With the current functionalities, the Knowledge Transfer Online Showcasing Module allows to:

- Find, filter and identify solutions to a specific topic/issue/need.
- Enhance visibility and findability of their Key Exploitable Result.
- Map stakeholders working in their area of interest.
- Draft Pathways to Impact in a graphical representation.
- Identify Synergies across Solutions, Projects and Stakeholders.
- Track impact based on the outcomes and impact indicators at pilot scale.

With the KTOSM, we provide a high-value, pioneering tool to prepare the first phase of the Mission Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030, fostering uptake, application and measurable impact, based on a tried and tested methodology, allowing for informing, visualising, undertaking and monitoring of the steps along the Pathway to Impact.

Building on the feedback and user-needs captured at the first live demonstration, as well as based on the needs identified in the Development of Pathways to Impact per high priority Key Exploitable Result (as described in the example provided in chapter 2.4), the team developed the KTOSM further, including A. a module specific for Network Analysis and Stakeholder Landscape Mapping (Figure 37), B. a graphical representation of Pathways to Impact, providing the possibility track the transfer impact per solution.

Figure 37: Access to “Explore the Stakeholder Landscape”

Clicking on “Explore the Stakeholder Landscape” (Figure 38), the new functionality of the Network Analysis and Stakeholder Landscape Mapping is shown.

Figure 38. Function “Explore the Stakeholder Landscape”

The nodes in the Stakeholder Landscape can be explored, expanded and connections can be seen between the solution, stakeholders, other projects, thematic categories and other solutions (Figure 38).

Both, the first feature, the pondered stakeholder listing in table-format, as shown in the figure below (Figure 39), as well as the graphical representation of the stakeholder graph, which pops-up when clicking on “view graph”, are maintained in the module. However, both are significantly enhanced.

Figure 39. Advanced functionalities of the KTOSM

The list of potential stakeholders includes a sophisticated AI-supported prioritisation/ranking of the stakeholders. In the first version, it was based on the number of “Matches”/ interlinkages across nodes. Through the sophisticated ranking, potential target stakeholder can be directly identified to the specification of an organisation. Based on the latest update, a ‘Match score’, shows how well stakeholders match the given solution, based on the number of shared EuroVoc terms between a stakeholder’s projects and the solution, weighted by the number of projects matching the solution.

When a right-click on the ‘Stakeholder’-node is performed, a direct link to the corresponding website is provided (Figure 40).

Figure 40. Direct link to the Stakeholder Website per Stakeholder Mapped

Furthermore, the network can be explored, as in the Stakeholder Mapping, with the possibility to expand the graph, by clicking on it. If a pathway to impact is available for a solution, the graphical representation of the Pathway to Impact can also be showcased (see Figure 41).

Stakeholder Graph

Figure 41. Advanced functionalities in the Stakeholder Graph

The graph above (Figure 41) shows an expanded network and a graphical representation of a Pathway to Impact, specific to a Solution. This Graphical representation of the Pathway to Impact is based on the other new module in the KTOSM: The graphical representation of Pathways to Impact, providing the possibility for monitoring the transfer impact per solution. It can be accessed by clicking on “Explore your Pathway to Impact”, as shown in the figure below (see Figure 42).

Figure 42 Access to “Explore your Pathway to Impact”

When accessing this module, the Pathway to impact is shown, with the functionality to add as many steps in the Pathway to Impact as needed (see Figure 43).

Explore your Pathway to Impact

Figure 43 Advanced functionalities in "Explore your Pathway to Impact" I

Moreover, also in this module, linkages to stakeholder can be mapped out as shown in the figure below (Figure 44):

Explore your Pathway to Impact

Figure 44 Advanced functionalities in "Explore your Pathway to Impact" II

The content of the Pathways to Impact can be introduced, specific to each Pathway developed. The Pathway to Impact can be informed e.g. based on expert panels, desktop-research and the Stakeholder Mapping in the KTOSM, among others. To introduce the Pathway to Impact, specific to a solution, a user would click on "Draft your Pathway to Impact" (see Figure 45).

Figure 45 Access to “Draft your Pathway to Impact”

Currently, only the core Team in PREP4BLUE, which developed the KTOSM has access to this function. In the next update, this function will be made available for each Knowledge Owner.

Based on the expert interviews and the landscape mapping supported by the Knowledge Transfer Online Showcasing Module, the pathways developed are deeply informed and a summary included in the Module, to allow impact monitoring towards the Mission Objectives and Targets.

The summary includes identified Transfer Activities, Target User, Applications, expected Outcomes and Transfer Impact Indicators.

Figure 46: Pathway Drafting Tool in the KTOSM.

This way, the KTOSM becomes a tool for a Knowledge Owner to draft their Pathway to impact (Figure 46) and monitor progress, as requested in the first live demonstration. Furthermore, the development of the pathways to impact, served as Case-Study for applying the Mission Ontology by FhA (see [D4.1 Report on INITIAL VERSION of Mission ontology and semantic network and guidance for use](#) and [D4.3 Report on FINAL Mission ontology / semantic network and guidance for use](#)), helping to capture and address the needs in the development of Pathways to Impact through the KTOSM. Specifically, stakeholder landscape mapping for potential target-user identification was identified as a critical need, which has now been addressed in the current version of the KTOSM.

4 Conclusions and Next Steps

The main objective of the PREP4BLUE project is to set the foundations for co-creating and co-implementing the research and innovation required to achieve the Mission. Therefore, tools, guidelines and methodologies were developed to support Mission stakeholders, facilitating their work towards achieving the Mission Objectives and Targets. As part of the work of PREP4BLUE, the Knowledge Transfer Online Showcasing Module (KTOSM) has been developed and successfully implemented.

The KTOSM is an AI-supported, interactive tool, designed to enhance knowledge management and impact monitoring. It provides interactive stakeholder landscape mapping, stakeholder ranking and facilitates Pathways to Impact drafting and visualisation for solutions with potential to support the Mission Objectives and Targets.

Several demonstrations of the KTOSM have been conducted, including live demonstrations, a demo video, and practical examples of Pathway to Impact development. These demonstrations have informed the development of the key functionalities of the tool, such as stakeholder landscape mapping and graphical representation of Pathways to Impact.

With these functions, the KTOSM empowers stakeholders to plan, undertake and track transfer activities. The possibility to develop outcome indicators based on the Knowledge Output at each transfer step, fosters a bottom-up, democratised and co-creative approach to the Mission progress tracking towards the Mission Objectives and Targets.

The next steps are focused on further developing and optimising the KTOSM to ensure optimal user experience and uptake of the tool. The partners are committed to enhancing the platform's innovative features and methodologies, which can be replicated in other initiatives, contributing to best practices in the field.

Immediate Development Goals:

- **Optimised User Experience:** continuously enhancing all functionalities of the KTOSM, in consideration of the FAIR principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability.

Medium-Term Development Goals

- **Impact Monitoring:** Develop a more sophisticated impact monitoring system to track and predict Mission progress and feature transfer success (uptake and application) and related impact.
- **Linkages Across Databases:** Enhance linkages across databases, including funding opportunities, policy and legislation.

Long-Term Development Goals:

- **Continued Involvement and Support:** Ensure long-term functionality and usefulness of the platform through continued involvement, support, and funding, especially through follow-on Mission Ocean and Waters projects.
- **Building Collaborations:** Continue to build collaborations to support the platform's development and functionality.